

THE ROLE OF CITIZENS IN MAINTAINING PUBLIC ORDER

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Annotation: the fact that our current peaceful and prosperous life is sustainable is first expressed in how the political system in the land is conducted and in what way citizens react to such policies being conducted. We know that maintaining peace in society is the duty of each of us.

Keywords: life, Citizen, state, politics, public order, opportunity, society, Control, Law, person.

Today, the development of our state in every area opens up a number of opportunities for our citizens. It is no secret that the changes taking place in various spheres of society are carried out directly on the basis of the active participation of citizens. The control of the activities of all state bodies implementing public policy is carried out not only by legislation, but also through public control. In this, the participation of citizens in maintaining order in public places can be evidence of our opinion. Let's think about what places are initially called public places in it. By public place we can understand the plot, buildings, structures and their parts, as well as transport communications of places that are allowed (to be) barrier-free access for everyone or that are intended to meet the different needs of citizens. According to World Scientists, public spaces are divided into 3 types:

1) public spaces of a permanent nature - such public spaces are public spaces that are classified by the possibility that citizens are permanent or permanent, are not defined by the Working Time regime and have permanent objects of residence of citizens, to which we can include transport highways, streets, residential themes, neighborhoods, geniuses, areas of small districts, airports, railway and car station buildings.

2) in public spaces of a temporary nature, we include public spaces that are classified by the possibility that citizens are temporary or are temporary, defined by the Working Time regime and in which there are no permanent objects of residence of citizens.

3) public spaces of a single tone, on the other hand, are objects where public public events are held, and objects of public public, agricultural and other (solemn events and religious ceremonies) events for the time of holding, as well as objects of individual areas.

The fact that our current peaceful and prosperous life is sustainable is primarily expressed in how the political system in the country is being conducted and in what way citizens react to such policies being conducted. We know that maintaining peace in society is the duty of each of us. But a thousand unfortunately, actions that negatively affect the development of our state and undermine the peace of our citizens still continue. European scholars have mentioned the following manifestations of public order disorders:

drinking alcohol in public places, (with the exception of places specially designated for these purposes) being drunk in public places;

participation in gambling for money, things and other valuable things in the yard, porch, Park, kindergarten, market, transport, beaches and other public places (except for places specially designed for these purposes);

insulting citizens in public places and other similar actions that disrupt public order and the peace of citizens.

access to freight trains, city trains and the stairs and buffers of intercity trains

passing through the carriageway of streets, railways in unknown places.

breaking silence by singing aloud, playing musical instruments; repairing an apartment using technical means

misuse of fire stairs, roofs, tents and basements of houses.

burning of garbage dumps around the house, near buildings, forest plantations and activating fires in the forest, bathing in prohibited places, rivers and ponds.

cut flowers from lawns and flower beds, collect protected wild plants, spoil or destroy green areas.

damage to railway, aviation, motor vehicle equipment, signalling and communications equipment, transportable equipment, containers and other property; throwing rocks and other objects at trains; placing items on railway tracks; access to service zones of air, water and rail transport.

storage of household and industrial waste in an unspecified place. Parking trucks between residential buildings and in courtyards. Driving on footpaths. Parking on lawns and playgrounds.

violation of pet care and walking rules.

sports and entertainment events, closing of stands, moving to stands, sports fields, running fields and other places to hold competitions or other events, as well as other actions that interfere with the holding of events.

the use of objects that create a noise effect and interfere with the audience, participants in sports and entertainment events, as well as obstacles, lighting devices, platforms for unloading television images, auxiliary structures for other purposes.

screams that belittle and humiliate the dignity of the organizers, performers and spectators of sports and entertainment events.

Organization of walks on the streets, squares and other public places after sports and entertainment events that interfere with the normal operation of transport or disrupt public order, etc.

From the examples presented above, we can say that the regulation of such disturbances, which at the moment can arise in all areas without the participation of citizens, again presents another new type of difficulties and problems. Therefore, it is necessary to instill in Citizens a passion for maintaining public order and instill in their minds the ideas of love, humanity, honesty and brotherhood in the motherland, instead of feelings of indifference and distrust towards society. Because many cases of disorder and offenses that are being committed, as well as crime, remain unopened precisely because of the indifference of citizens, their unwillingness to help others or their unwillingness to take their time away. This creates a number of problems not only in the Prevention of crime, but also in their detection and elimination.

As you know, social tension in society is sharply increased in emergency situations: natural disasters, major accidents and disasters, epidemics, mass killings, social and political

crises, acts of terrorism. In such situations, the presence of public structures that contribute to the protection of law enforcement and the elimination of the consequences of emergency situations is of vital importance. These factors lead to the need to seek additional mechanisms for maintaining public order, including the creation of public or public-state organizations of Citizens for the protection of Public Order, and formalize them in legislation.

In modern conditions, in the provision of public order protection, law enforcement regime, it is required to actively involve the public in the creation of conditions for citizens to provide comprehensive assistance to the internal affairs bodies.

Of the scientists who conducted research within the framework of this topic, Ya.Ya. Kyle et al.V.The yepininas analyze the application of the mechanism of citizen participation in maintaining public order in the United Kingdom, United States, Spain, Norway and other countries.

In their opinion, the more actively the participation of citizens in the activities of the public administration system is carried out, that is, the wider the involvement of citizens in public affairs, the more successfully the political and economic spheres develop. That being said, the participation of citizens in the maintenance of Public Order first of all, it is important to determine the measures of this participation, the methods of participation and the forms of interaction between the authorities and the population.

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